

Classics and Canon in Secondary Education: Exploring the Thinking of 30 Literature Teachers in Spain

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Abstract

The controversy surrounding the canon since the 1970s, as well as the multicultural nature of contemporary societies, has led to the emergence of several studies, both empirical and based on teachers' beliefs, which analyse how the reading of the classics fits into this new plural context. However, there are no such approaches in Spain from the teachers' perspective. To address this issue, a qualitative case study is presented based on interviews with 30 secondary school teachers. Data were analysed thematically and coded with NVivo 12 software, resulting in the identification of four main categories: teacher beliefs about their relationship with the classics, knowledge, beliefs about the sociocultural factor, and teaching practices and strategies. The findings reveal that teachers think it is important to read the classics, but they also argue that they must be approached in ways that engage students in interpreting them.

Keywords

Classic authors, teacher beliefs, canon, secondary education

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Clásicos y Canon en la Educación Secundaria: Explorando el Pensamiento de 30 Profesores de Literatura en España

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Resumen

La controversia en torno al canon desde los años setenta, así como el carácter multicultural de las sociedades contemporáneas, ha propiciado la aparición de diversos estudios, tanto empíricos como basados en las creencias de los profesores, que analizan cómo encaja la lectura de los clásicos en este nuevo contexto plural. Sin embargo, en España no existen aproximaciones de este tipo desde la perspectiva del profesorado. Para abordar esta cuestión, se presenta un estudio de caso cualitativo basado en entrevistas a 30 profesores de Secundaria. Los datos se analizaron temáticamente y se codificaron con el software NVivo 12, dando como resultado la identificación de cuatro categorías principales: creencias de los profesores sobre su relación con los clásicos, conocimientos, creencias sobre el factor sociocultural y prácticas y estrategias de enseñanza. Los resultados revelan que los profesores creen que es importante leer a los clásicos, pero también sostienen que deben abordarse de manera que los alumnos participen en su interpretación.

Palabras clave

Autores clásicos, creencias docentes, canon, educación secundaria

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The concepts of ‘classic’ and ‘canon’ have been interpreted in many different ways over time. The term *classici* describe manifestations that are exemplary for their excellence, as they represent the best version on a given language (Eliot, 1957). Classic authors are admired and read down through the generations, regardless of the era and fleeting trends and tastes (Gadamer, 1989). Classics are timeless because they can elicit a fresh interpretation from each reading and reader (Eliot, 1957). However, the classics cannot be removed from the time in which they were created, as they often portray a culture’s collective memory (Calvino, 1999).

The literary canon refers to a body of imitable works and authors bestowed with authority (Eaglestone, 1999). The idea of the canon originated in the nineteenth century and has since changed with developments in society in each period of history. The appearance of the first histories of literature and the romantic view that each nation had a soul with defining characteristics led to the modern concept of the canon as a body of works that can convey each country’s collective heritage and historical narrative (Harris, 1991). However, this concept of the canon—tied to ideas of authority and nation—was challenged in the late twentieth century, when various cultural and political movements, like deconstruction theory and cultural studies, began to question who determines the canon and what is excluded. Consequently, two stances emerged: on the one hand, there were those who criticised the canon for its exclusionary nature, as the selection ignored multiple groups such as women, racialised writers and writers of diverse sexual orientations. In contrast, the latter advocated an aesthetic vision of literature (Sullá, 1998), which advocates liberating literature from any political and politicised meaning.

In this climate of polarisation, systemic theories emerged as an alternative to these opposing views, analysing culture as a global system (Even-Zohar, 1997). Without wading into the controversy about whether or not a canon should exist, systemic theories focused on the external factors that determine canonical selection. According to this framework, true universality does not lie in aesthetic criteria but rather in the tension and movement taking place between the elements of the system (Benton, 2000). Thus, each cultural system consists of a centre, where the works of the canon are located, and a periphery, populated by those struggling to become canonical (Even-Zohar, 1997). However, this centre-periphery structure is not static, according to Even-Zohar (1997), the intervention of certain actors—such as institutions, the authors themselves, the market, metatexts and readers—can drive works on the periphery into the centre, and vice versa. In fact, the prominence of readers after the emergence of the Aesthetics of Reception has overturned the ‘table of values’ (Bourdieu, 1984). As a result, groups that previously felt ignored by the canon propose vocational canons, using these repertoires to represent cultural and vocational values in terms of the race, class and gender that their members share (Mignolo, 1991). Thus, the concept of canon has lost some autonomy, as voices have emerged questioning its selection and its legitimacy, a challenge further amplified by the horizontal and subversive dynamics of the Internet (Lluch, 2014).

In summary, while the concepts of classic and canon can be delimited, it can sometimes be challenging to irrevocably conclude that a particular author is classic, canonical or both. Nevertheless, it is undeniable that whereas classic works are characterised by offering multiple interpretations, the canon is constructed based on how the texts are read, and not on the texts themselves (Benton, 2000). Unlike classic texts, which outlast trends and official interpretations, the canon is instituted as a historical narration.

Teacher Beliefs about Reading Classic Authors in Secondary Education

The analysis of teacher cognition is considered one of the most valued fields of study in educational research (Wang et al., 2018), due to the leading role played by the teacher in the educational system. This paradigm analyses what teachers know and believe about aspects that are part of the profession, including their didactics (Schutz et al., 2020). Given the importance of the teacher's concept of literature (Myren-Svelstad & Grütters, 2022), an increasing number of studies explore teachers' thoughts on reading the classics.

This area consists mainly of qualitative research studies based on interviews, such as the study by Sanjuán (2013), the first to explore this topic in Spain, although it does not really focus on the teaching of the classics, but rather on the analysis of the emotional components of literary reading in childhood and adolescence. Rezaul and Hussain (2021) do focus on the teaching of the classics, illustrating the beliefs of two English teachers in India about reading Shakespeare in secondary education, as do López-Rodríguez and Núñez-Delgado (2023), in which 12 secondary school teachers from Spain participate, a country that also serves as the setting for the work of Hernández-Heras et al., (2024), based on interviews with six expert teachers. Other studies analyse content using open questionnaires, like the one conducted by Athanases and Sánchez (2020), who interview 46 secondary school teachers in California, and the one carried out by Myren-Svelstad and Grütters (2022), involving 65 informants from Norway. There are also some quantitative approaches, such as the studies by Elliott and Olive (2021, 2023), which surveyed 211 teachers from the United Kingdom using a closed questionnaire.

In this context, teachers emphasise the importance of canonical authors because of the benefits they bring to the identity and education of young readers, which in turn highlights the meanings that informants attribute to the category of classic. In this way, the stories told in these works can serve as guidance for young people in any life situation. Since they have left their mark on literature and art, knowing them not only allows for a better interpretation of any artistic expression, but also greater enjoyment. Due to their quality, classics grant the implicit reader great freedom, as they do not present a single meaning. Since they perfectly portray the context in which they were created, they are essential for understanding the history, art and society of other times (Athanases & Sánchez, 2020; Elliott & Olive, 2021, Myren & Grütters, 2022; Sanjuán, 2013). Thus, in the studies by Hernández-Heras et al., (2024) and by López-Rodríguez and Núñez Delgado (2023), the teachers declare their love for these texts by virtue of their timeless themes, humour and characters. Nevertheless, these studies also note that it is becoming increasingly difficult to cover them in the classroom.

According to the informants, this is due to the difficulties that students face when reading them. To explain these challenges, our study has been adapted to the classification by Steiner (1978), initially created to characterise the complexities that arise when reading poetry. Firstly, readers experience contingent difficulties because they lack the knowledge necessary to decode the text. This is usually due to their low level of linguistic competency or because they are not familiar with the text's sociocultural references (Hernández-Heras et al., 2024; López-Rodríguez & Núñez-Delgado, 2023). However, such difficulties can be overcome with certain resources, such as dictionaries and the teacher's assistance.

Nevertheless, even when students do have this knowledge, some aspects remain unintelligible to them because they cannot empathise with certain fictional worlds. This is not due to the discourse, but simply because of the students themselves; maybe the works are too distant, they lack maturity (Hernández-Heras et al., 2024) or the students feel rejected by the dominant ideology that the texts convey in terms of race, class or gender (Rezaul & Hussain, 2021). In this regard, teachers highlight the socio-demographic differences between the authors and classic stories and the increasingly multicultural student body. All these types of difficulties are called modal difficulties, which may not be easily resolved through research, but could be overcome over time. There are authors whose works might not resonate with a reader initially, but that same reader could later find them meaningful after going through personal struggles or experiences.

Unlike the difficulties that arise in the reader, tactical ones emerge from the text itself. These occur when authors intentionally introduce confusion to challenge the reader. Some teachers view this as a strategy to guide readers along the path laid by the author (López-Rodríguez & Núñez-Delgado, 2023).

To overcome these challenges, the teachers of the studies defend adopting didactic methods based on students' reading responses, even though the reading of classics in classrooms in Spain has long been associated with traditional approaches such as historicist and structuralist approaches (Sanjuán, 2013; López-Rodríguez & Núñez-Delgado, 2023), which focus on the memorisation of facts and mechanical textual analysis. In search of aesthetic reading experiences that renew old paradigms, teachers stress the importance of establishing connections between the world of the text and the world of their students (Myren & Grütters, 2022) through gateway activities that give them deep access to the text (Elliot & Olive, 2023; Hernández-Heras et al., 2024; Rezaul & Hussain, 2021). Ultimately, it is about making them understand that reading the classics is useful in itself, since, when properly guided, it will shape their character.

On the other hand, teachers who are aware of the cultural differences between authors and classic stories and their students propose reading the classics through Critical Canon Pedagogy. In the Anglo-Saxon context—where the debate about the composition and selection of the canon arose—, this approach seeks to deconstruct the dominant ideologies that underpin the texts that have been canonised. Teachers seek to foster students' socio-political awareness through literary discussion and a constant questioning of texts as political works. Although most of these studies analyse teaching experiences, some reveal the beliefs of teachers regarding canonical readings, who declare themselves to be at odds with the curriculum because it forces them to transmit a Euro-exclusive repertoire (Steiss, 2012). This is confirmed, for example, by Sam, the teacher interviewed by Dyches (2018). In his testimony, Sam observes that some students do not identify at all with the characters in the works, who are from a different social class and ethnicity, and even feel that reading them is an act of micro-aggression ('micro-support').

The controversy that has surrounded the canon since the 1970s, as well as the multicultural nature of contemporary societies, has led to the emergence of several studies, both empirical (Dyches, 2018; Steiss, 2020) and based on teachers' beliefs (Rezaul and Hussain, 2021), which analyse how the reading of the classics fits into this new plural context, especially in the Anglo-Saxon countries. However, since the teaching of literature in Spain has been mainly based on

biographical-contextual and structuralist approaches, we have not found research that studies how teachers currently interact with the new socio-cultural framework in which teachers and their students find themselves during the reading of classics in secondary school. For this reason, the following study is based on the following research questions: What is teachers' relationship with classical authors like? How have they internalised the concepts of classic and canon? How do they consider that the new socio-cultural framework affects the teaching of classics? What practices do they consider optimal for transmitting classics in this new context.

Method

The following research explores teachers' beliefs about teaching the classics through semi-structured interviews within the framework of a case study. The case study was chosen for the present study because it fits the objectives and research questions. Due to its revealing potential, it facilitates the emergence of knowledge. Since it promotes the transitivity of participants' experiences, it allows us to produce what is meaningful in the qualitative paradigm: experiential knowledge (Geertz, 1973), which forms the basis of our object of analysis.

Context and Participants

The study involved 30 teachers of Spanish language and literature in Aragon, an autonomous community in Spain with approximately 1,200 teachers in these subjects. The recruitment process involved contacting the administrations of all public, charter, and private schools in the community. The project was explained to them, and they were invited to participate in the study. Participant selection followed a theoretical sampling process (Glaser & Straus, 1967), and the inclusion of new participants ceased when no additional data were found that could enrich the constructed categories.

All the interviews began with sociodemographic questions (Table 1). There is a predominance of women and more experienced informants, which coincides with the distribution of the community, according to the Spanish National Institute of Statistics (INS). The schools' percentages of immigrant students were sorted into three categories—low, medium and high—using national sociodemographic data taken from INS.

Table 1*Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Informants and Their Schools*

Variable	Descriptor	Frecuency (%)
Sex	Female	70
	Male	30
Age	Under 35	33.3
	36 to 45	26.7
	46 to 55	10
	Over 55	30
Level of immigration	Low	26.7
	Moderate	40
	High	33.3
Neighbourhood average gross income per capita level	Low	26.7
	Moderate	50
	High	23.3

Data Analysis

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, with questions posed in an open-ended and non-directive manner. The interviews were recorded, with a total duration of 16 hours and 21 minutes and were then transcribed in full. The thematic analysis (Gibbs, 2012) of the interviews followed a categorical framework based on the previous theoretical framework, but reworked ad hoc (Kvale, 1996) to adapt to the emergency process. The steps involved in this thematic analysis include understanding the data obtained, coding from the existing data, and forming themes or patterns from the existing coding.

In this way, several preliminary categories were created taking the research questions as a basis (Elliott, 2018): personal relationship with the classics, knowledge, beliefs about the sociocultural factor, and practices and strategies. After analysing the data, these preliminary categories were transformed into macro-categories, which led to the identification of new categories and subcategories. As for their names, some come from expressions that reproduce the exact words of the participants, which allows for the construction of codes and subsequently fully emerging themes that bring the researcher closer to the voices of the participants they are intended to reflect (Creswell, 2015). Others come from terms coined by theory, such as ‘knowledge’, and others have been developed by the researcher based on their conceptual and structural unity (Elliott, 2018).

The data were subsequently coded using NVivo12 software. In addition to evaluating the saturation of macro-categories, categories, and subcategories, a set of descriptors was developed to better define the content of these structures. The number of references and saturation percentages across different structures were considered in relation to the sociodemographic variables of the school or the teacher. Therefore, they are considered mixed forms of data analysis that allow for the quantification of findings and frequencies of emerging codes, given the usefulness of numbers in interpreting observations (Sandelowski, 2001). However, these variables were included only when the discourse indicated their relevance, as numerical data are secondary in qualitative methodology.

The macro-category ‘personal relationship with the classics’ (Table 2) includes beliefs related to the participants, such as how they conceptualise themselves and how they feel as readers.

Table 2

Scheme of the Macro-Category ‘Personal Relationship with the Classics’

Categories	Subcategories	Characteristics
Reader profile	Vocational	Frequent reading of classic works for pleasure and for education
	Professional	Intermittent reading of classic works connected to their profession

The macro-category ‘knowledge’ (Table 3) focuses on the concepts of canon and classic internalised by the informants.

Table 3

Scheme of the Macro-Category ‘Knowledge’

Categories	Subcategories	Characteristics
Conceptualisation of canon and classic	Concepts of canon and classic	Difficulties in the conceptual definition Hard-to-access works Chronological conception of the concept of ‘classic’
	Criteria of attribution to the concept of classic	Transmission of cultural and intellectual heritage Catalyst for intertextual and intercultural connections Applicability of themes, values and ideas to the present Expansion of reality Models of style (<i>auctoritas</i> and <i>imitatio</i>) Source of pleasure

The preliminary category ‘beliefs about the sociocultural factor’ was transformed into a macro-category (Table 4) composed of three categories, which vary depending on the student’s relationship with the classics according to their insertion in different contextual frameworks: the current cultural system, the school and their maturing stage, adolescence.

Table 4
Scheme of the Macro-Category ‘Sociocultural Factor’

Categories	Subcategories	Characteristics
Current cultural framework	Role of the classic in current culture	Reading classics as a symbol of distinction Humanities’ loss of prestige Difficulties in reading classics due to the proliferation of stimuli in the digital age Lack of reading culture in Spain
	Stances on the transmission of classical works in education	Deconstruction of the model of the white bourgeois adult male for being socially exclusive Reconstruction of the literary canon for its aesthetic value
Sociodemographic characteristics of the school	Characteristics of the environment	Sociodemographic characteristics of the neighbourhood Neighbourhood resources
	Characteristics of the school	Students’ demographic profile School resources
Maturational characteristics of the students	Cultural preferences	Cultural apathy Reading habits
	Attitude	Initial resistance to literature
	Aptitude	Contingent difficulties Modal difficulties Tactical difficulties

The macro-category ‘teaching practices and strategies’ (Table 5) is divided into three categories. Firstly, teachers’ general position on reading the classics from 1st year of secondary education to 2nd year of Bachillerato, with two stances: for or against. Next, two approaches are identified: one based on reception and the traditional approach. The last category addresses didactical transpositions.

Table 5*Scheme of the Macro-Category 'Teaching Practices and Strategies'*

Categories	Subcategories	Characteristics
General position on reading the classics from Years 8 to 13	For	Challenges for students Core of literary history
	Against	Difficulties in instilling reading habits
Approach	Reception-based	Non-historicist organisation of knowledge Use of active methodologies Evaluation of the process Dialogic activities Expansion of the curricular canon Promotion of the pleasure of reading
	Traditional	Students' independent reading Exam-based evaluation of results Use of reading control Use of the participative lecture Promotion of knowledge
Didactical transpositions	Models of success	Importance of how: linking the work to the student's current situation Importance of reading in class to 'translate' the work Importance of motivation and the teacher's knowledge Importance of the selection of the works

Ethical Considerations

The entire process followed the instructions of the Autonomous Community of Aragon's Research Ethics Committee. Before conducting the interviews, the authors read a form stipulating the limits of the research and committed the researchers to safeguard the anonymity and confidentiality of the responses in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). The interviews began once the informant had accepted the protocol.

Results

Macro-category ‘personal relationship with the classics’

Figure 1

Saturation of ‘Vocational Reader’ and ‘Professional Reader’

The distribution of teachers with a professional reader profile and teachers with a vocational reader profile is quite similar (Figure 1). Professional readers only read classics for work-related reasons. Therefore, they only reread classics or read other works they did not previously know because it is required for the subject they teach. They are currently inclined to more contemporary alternatives because they associate them with reading for entertainment, although nearly all say that they enjoy teaching the classics. Vocational readers of classic books stand out by completely blurring the boundaries between their professional and personal perspectives, as such works determine how they feel and think: “Teacher29: I love the classics; they have really and fully marked how I understand life and human relationships. I just can’t imagine my everyday life without a classic book nearby.”

Age seems to be a determining factor here. This is demonstrated by the heat map in Figure 2, in which 66.7% of the professional readers are under 35 years old, whereas 55.56% of the vocational readers are over 55. However, there are also professional readers of classics in other age groups, yet no vocational readers are under 35.

Figure 2

Saturation of the Professional Reader and Vocational Reader Profiles by Age. Cell Values Correspond to Row Percentages

Reader profile	Under 35 years	36 to 45	46 to 55	Over 55
Professional	66.67	8.33	8.33	16.67
Vocational	0	33.33	11.11	55.56

In this regard, vocational readers over 55 reflect on having grown up under the paradigm of the classics and the cultural canon. They acknowledge that both concepts were once indisputable, fully legitimised categories that were not subject to debate by either students or society. They refer to a cultural model that authorised the status of the classics and expanded their sphere of influence to all areas of life: the canon and the classics not only served as artistic manifestations, but above all, as concepts, ever-linked to the ideas of benchmark and model. Due to that unquestionable presence, these teachers have never looked into what classic and canonical mean, because they had always been there and had to be:

Teacher29: There is the fact that we grew up with them: they were given to us. We definitely haven't thought about what they were and we haven't often stopped to think about, well, their implications, but the word 'classic' was very recognisable. The classics... so, we can recognise them, but... to define them, well, we would need to work on that.

Macro-Category 'Knowledge'

One of the reasons why some teachers have difficulty in specifying what either concept means may be due to how they have so uncritically taken them for granted, to the point of merging the academic literature's definitions of each. Thus, they use the ideas of classic and canon indiscriminately or mix up the formative canon with the literary canon. In other instances, lacking a clear definition of the concept of the classic, they define it by opposition, mainly chronologically. As such, they define what it means by establishing what it is not and come to view the classics as excellent works of literature written from Greek and Roman times to the present day.

Other teachers ground their perspectives on the degree of access to their meanings. They view the classics as challenging to read and especially interpreted and enjoyed by readers with a certain level of cultural knowledge. This is primarily because the texts have to be deciphered, which is sometimes a hurdle, even for teachers, whether due to their language or conceptual complexity. Teachers' view of classics as artistic manifestations that put readers to the test shows that they consider teaching them to be challenging not only for themselves but especially for their students, who are hardly their implied readers:

Teacher8: I don't think it's the cultural level, much less that of today's teenagers, but it's often not even my own: there are canonical books that I'm not prepared for. Góngora may be canonical and whatever else you want to call it, but I don't understand Góngora.

However, the teachers tend to agree on the characteristics that the academic literature attributes to the concept of classic. Of the six identified, the most influential in their interviews recognises the applicability of the themes, stances, values and ideas of classic works in the present (Figure 3), although there is a very similar distribution between this item and the one about the transmission of cultural and intellectual heritage.

Figure 3

Saturation of the Subcategory 'Criteria of Attribution to the Category of Classics'

In this regard, the teachers stress the timeless value of classic books, which endures due to their homogenising nature: even though the teachers admit that there is a great cultural divide and gap in time between their students and the classics, they acknowledge they are shaped by the same mould. It is this similarity as human beings belonging to the same species that must serve as a bridge between both worlds and as a starting point for teaching the classics. Thus, classic literature provides an excellent example of the evolution of certain themes that remain relevant because they are inherent to human beings, such as love, revenge and death:

Teacher25: Well, look, my student Pepito, who doesn't read anymore, spends all day on his mobile phone. He watches Netflix and all that, but in the end he has the same something or other as Garcilaso, because he is a human being and because there is something there that endures, right?

While the teachers interviewed opt for going beyond the context of the works to engage their students through the major themes, they also advocate for the heritage and national nature

of this literature; the classics may not know borders, but they do have roots. Thus, their depiction of a certain time and place is essential to the consolidation of cultural unity. The teachers regret the loss of a shared cultural identity:

Teacher11: In previous times, literature was almost the basis of a moral education, but also of a historical and social education. You taught children that they belonged to a literary realism. You could also use the classics to tell them about belonging to a culture. But these days, that is all completely watered down.

Furthermore, the classics expand the edges of reality through the fictional world they cast. According to the teachers, another feature that defines a classic is its excellence. As a result, they are models that deserve to be imitated, insofar as readers aspire to hone their literary and linguistic skills. The teachers also view classics as catalysts of intertextual and intercultural connections. They see them as works that enrich us intellectually, emotionally, culturally and in terms of identity. Finally, despite being the criterion that they mention the least, they also believe that classics are those books that their readers simply enjoy.

Macro-Category ‘Beliefs about the Sociocultural Factor’

According to the informants, the classics no longer play a leading role in culture, mainly because of the proliferation of stimuli of the digital age, which satisfy teenagers’ short-term appetites. As a result, their attention spans have shrunk and their ability to understand has weakened, so they can only read short texts. Furthermore, since they are attached to popularity rankings, those active on social media need to appeal to users’ feelings to gain visibility. This ad hoc production for public consumption is completely at odds with the characteristics of a classic text, which has no place in these fashionable trends.

As a result, the digital world has displaced the traditional canonisation system with its own selection process. A paradigm shift has taken place: in contrast to the vertical hierarchy of the past, where, for example, criticism infused authority, the Internet has invented a parallel universe with its own rules. As a consequence, young people have lost respect for the authority that the canon previously enshrined because they have found other cultural beacons to follow:

Teacher 2: There is also the fact that they no longer have that concept of authority—not just the content, but not even the idea, right? It’s like they rebel against that. I have always bought magazines like *Cinemanía* to skim through and decide which movies to watch, but I cannot imagine my students doing that in their lives. They’re not interested in what some stuffy middle-aged men say. They're interested in what the people they follow on social media say.

Having already discussed the teachers’ views on the role of the classics in our culture today, the focus now shifts to the place that they think they deserve. As shown in Figure 4, the indicator ‘deconstruction of the model of the white bourgeois adult male for being socially exclusive’ is saturated at a higher percentage than ‘reconstruction of the literary canon for its aesthetic value’.

Figure 4

Saturation of the Characteristics of the Subcategory ‘Stances on the Transmission of Classical Works in Education’

Therefore, some teachers opt for deconstructing the literary canon because it has been selected according to the model of the white bourgeois adult male, which has distorted literary perspectives in terms of gender, race and class. Laid down according to an androcentric and patriarchal ideology, the canon has not only shaped the profiles of its authors, but also those of the main characters of the canonised works. In fact, several teachers state that the canon also excludes those who do not yet have the knowledge necessary to understand it due to their lack of education. As a result, being part of the canon also implies being part of a cultural elite that can only be accessed by means of economic privilege. “Teacher 2: Are they great works? Yes, but they have that more selective component. It’s kind of the history of the white, heterosexual man.”

As an alternative, some teachers suggest a plurality of repertoires instead of a single canon endowed with all literary authority. Others would not seek to suppress what is canonical, but advocate for expanding the canon to include other perspectives, thereby giving visibility to all sides of history. In contrast to society in the past, which accepted the model of the white bourgeois adult male, today’s cultural paradigm is much more diverse and is no longer reflected in this canonical construction. This can be detrimental, since everyone needs benchmarks. Thus, they conflate the ideas of canon and identity, as they want to expand the canon so all their students can feel included in literature:

Teacher 2: Before, everyone accepted the culture that was handed down to them because it was completely hegemonic. White people, heterosexuals... and literature was written about them, and the others were silenced. But now there are new identities that no longer tolerate that view because they are not represented. The other day we were reading Don Juan and a girl said to me: 'How does this girl allow this stuff?' They really don't know how to distance themselves, do they?

Other teachers argue that the canon operates autonomously, so there is no need to change it. They underscore the quality of the works as the only valid criterion, asserting that the canon's capacity for self-regulation will naturally incorporate authors that deserve to enter it. They also warn that prioritising ideological issues over literary ones can distort the very idea of the canon, reducing it to a framework that loses the hierarchical and exemplary essence of the original concept. Furthermore, while the criterion of quality can become operative through more or less objective precepts, they note that imposing boundaries is more complex when the primary requirement is social justice, which can prompt the boundless canonisation of any type of reality.

Regarding influence of the environment on the teaching of classics, teachers who teach in schools with high levels of immigration and in schools with a low average gross income per capita have more references in all categories (Figure 5).

Figure 5

Number of References in the Category of the Sociodemographic Characteristics of the School Based on the Level of Immigration and the Neighbourhood's Average Gross Income per Capita

Subcategory	Indicator	Level of immigration			Neighbourhood average gross income per capita		
		Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High
Characteristics of the school	Students' demographic profile	2	0	7	7	1	1
	School resources	2	0	3	4	1	0
Characteristics of the environment	Sociodemographic characteristics of the neighbourhood	2	2	2	6	0	0
	Neighbourhood resources	0	0	2	2	0	0

The informants consider the demographic context of the environment to be crucial, particularly in the most disadvantaged settings. They report expending additional effort to compensate for the social inequalities their students face. Furthermore, establishing connections between the school and its surrounding community not only improves the quality of life for residents, but also offers students valuable personal benefits, as they can see how their efforts have an impact on their environment.

The school's resources also shape teaching practices, since some schools lack the necessary materials. However, the schools' most influential indicator is their students' demographic profile. When students suffer from disorderly home environments or financial problems, reading the classics is last on their list of priorities. Some informants attempt to mitigate these

problems from the start, trying to use knowledge as a civilising mechanism and a tool for social mobility. By taking a performative approach, literature can also serve as a form of therapy that buffers students from their hostile circumstances: “Teacher 2: As a teacher, you try to smooth things over, giving them some escape so they don’t have to stay stuck in their situation from the start.”

Regarding the characteristics of students as individuals in the context of adolescence, teachers tend to attribute a fairly consistent profile to them. First, they note a lack of curiosity about culture. Since they neither read nor are they familiar with the most prominent authors in their surrounding environment, teachers and students live different worlds. Overall, the students tend to resist reading classic literature due to the distance in time and difficulty that they associate with it. Since the classics are linked to a time and a culture so far removed from their own, students feel no immediate connection and cannot understand why they should read these works.

However, students’ motivations for reading the classics are not the only relevant factor, as the complexities stemming from their abilities are equally important. For example, there are contingent difficulties. Students’ limited semantic competency prevents them from even understanding the discourse on a literal level, leading to multiple confusions. On other occasions, students do not understand the works because they have forgotten or still lack the contextual knowledge that classical literature requires for interpretation. As a result, they cannot access the text’s horizon of expectations. When such contingent difficulties are so pronounced, the mediator’s role becomes essential to fill these gaps.

At times, students feel that the books are far removed from their own ways of thinking and living. Even if they possess some historical and semantic knowledge, there are still elements that remain unintelligible to them. Regarding these modal complexities, students struggle to transcend their individual consciousness and understand other ways of life. This is especially challenging for them when the values they are expected to engage with are tied to a national cultural identity. The informants note that their students do not empathise with books that detail relatively recent events because they never experienced that Spain: “Teacher3: In the end, they are heirs to that Spain, but they do not empathise with it. Look, these are deeply rooted issues in our culture, but they seem foreign to them.”

Finally, students must also overcome tactical difficulties that authors have deliberately programmed for their readers. When the students manage to solve the puzzle, their feeling of self-efficacy rises considerably. They also experience other gratifying feelings like the strangeness effect.

Macro-Category ‘Beliefs about Teaching Practices and Strategies’**Figure 6**

Saturation of the Items of the Category ‘General Position on Reading the Classics’

Teachers report more positive than negative aspects when students 1st year of secondary education to 2nd year of Bachillerato read classic works (Figure 6), which they consider the core of their subject as it is the pinnacle of the history of literature. This perspective, aligned with their patrimonial view of the concept of classic, is based on the premise that the history of literature can only be explained through its most significant authors. While some teachers assert that the legitimacy of classical works is beyond question, others challenge this view due to the difficulties these works create in fostering reading habits among students. Thus, they believe that classic literature should yield to contemporary literature, which they argue would be more useful to them.

Figure 7
Saturation of the 'Approach' Subcategories

The reception-based approach is more common than the traditional one (Figure 7). However, no teacher profile exclusively adopts either the reception-based or traditional model. The reception-based approach aims to ease students' access to the classics, ensuring that their first experience is at least rewarding, with the potential for developing deeper appreciation over time. This approach emphasises a non-historicist organisation of knowledge, the use of new methodologies, the expansion of the curricular canon, process-related evaluation and, above all, dialogic activities that motivate students' reading responses. These activities may be standardised, like literary discussion groups, or less formal, like spontaneous conversations. In either case, the aim is to pique students' interest in current social or political issues like gender perspective, racism or corruption as a way to explore classic literature, and vice versa, thereby establishing a two-way relationship between the context of the student and the context of the book. Teachers observe that when students are actively involved in the learning process, their interest grows.

From a historicist perspective that prioritises the author's coded interpretation over the student's personal processing, the traditional approach pursues the transmission of knowledge to cultivate general cultural literacy among students. This is typically achieved through interactive lectures, independent reading by students, and result-based assessment.

Given the heterogeneity of students, finding universally successful strategies for teaching the classics in secondary education can be challenging. However, certain principles are essential to achieving success. Ordered by percentage of saturation, these include highly motivated teachers, carefully selected texts, reading in the classroom to help students decode the works due to their contingent difficulties and focus on the historical perspective.

All teachers agree that students cannot fully understand or appreciate the classics without the guidance of their teacher. These texts will help students shape their identities only if the teachers become personally involved. Through this contagious nature of literature, the classics are humanised by the subjective element introduced by the mediators, making them more accessible and relatable. Moreover, that passion has given them a better understanding of the academic subject at hand, which will help them to succeed in their teaching approach.

Teacher 5: The better you know the book and the more you can develop, expand and show passion for it, the more likely you are to hook them. If Don Quixote doesn't excite you, you won't be able to convey passion for Don Quixote.

Conclusion and Discussion

This research focuses on the beliefs of 30 teachers of Spanish language and literature about reading the classics in secondary education. Thus, the study is framed within the qualitative line that prevails in this field of study. This study has demonstrated that the participants have a consolidated reading habit, although there are two profiles depending on their relationship with the classics: professional readers and vocational readers. Unlike other studies focused on types of readers, which use labels such as 'weak reader' and 'strong reader' (Munita, 2013), the specific characteristics of literature teachers has led to this new categorisation. As noted by López-Rodríguez and Núñez-Delgado (2023), it seems that the more experienced a teacher is, the stronger their bond with the classics.

Despite confusing the concepts of canon and classic, the teachers do suggest some features of the concept of classic that echo many of those attributed by the specialised literature, notably its excellence (Eliot, 1957), timelessness (Gadamer, 1989) and universality (Bloom, 1995; Harvey et al., 2020). However, what teachers stress most about the classics is that they help to unify and transmit cultural identity (Myren & Grüters, 2022). In this way, the teachers have inherited the original meaning of canonical when the concept emerged in the nineteenth century (Harris, 1991). As such, the teachers relate the classic with an integrating concept of both universal and national identity.

This study has shown the need to consider the students' cultural framework. The informants are heirs to the debate about the configuration of the canon that emerged in the late twentieth century. Some teachers criticise the current selection, based on the model of the white bourgeois adult male, because it is part of a mythologisation that supports the entitlement of the curriculum (Bourdieu, 1984). This is reported in some empirical studies (Dyches, 2018) that show how this highbrow literature, which is not accessible to just any reader due to its complexity, can exclude those who do not have the knowledge necessary to understand the works.

As an alternative, some support the plurality of vocational canons (Mignolo, 1991) and others opt for opening the canon to writers who represent minorities (Benton, 2000). This demonstrates that part of the sample sees literature as a 'mirror and window' (Bishop, 1990), so their proposals maintain the link between identity and the canon that led to these selections. In contrast to this deconstructivist approach, other teachers take essentialist stances, calling for

a conception of literature free of any political or politicised meaning and based on the belief that there are immutable principles of beauty (Bloom, 1995).

From this sociocultural perspective, this research study has shown that the school's resources also shape teaching practices, especially in schools that lack them or where there is a high proportion of immigration and low average gross income (Bokiev & Ismail, 2021). In such cases, teachers use literature as a democratising and transformative mechanism in an attempt to practise culturally responsible pedagogy (Dyches, 2018).

In line with previous studies (Yang, 2022), this contribution has revealed that adolescents hardly read these types of books because they pose three kinds of problems (Steiner, 1978). As reported in some empirical studies, the students encounter contingent difficulties due to their weak grasp of semantics (Wood, 2017) and their poor knowledge of the socio-historical context of these classic works (Matruglio & Vale, 2019). In other cases, students do not understand the books (modal difficulties), because they cannot empathise with the characters, who live in a different world than their own, despite being part of the same cultural system. This corroborates the findings of some studies (Antonsich, 2009) that highlight the lack of a sense of national belonging that characterises young people's identity today. Finally, students also face some tactical difficulties that the authors deliberately programmed into their works.

Furthermore, the students' habitus (Bourdieu, 1984) is contrary to that of the teachers, since the exemplary connotations of the concept of classic have lost their value. The digital world has given all power to the prosumer (Toffler, 1980) at the expense of those who dictated the traditional rules of canonisation, such as institutions and the market. Thus, young people have established their own repertoire, irrespective of how it relates to the official one. Doing the work previously performed by metatexts (Even-Zohar, 1997), influencers determine the readings established on any product. In this sense, although social networks and platforms promote their own counter-canon, the canonical model is still operational.

Despite the difficulties posed by interacting with students, most teachers believe that secondary school students should read the classics (Elliot & Olive, 2019). As reported in some empirical research focused on the reception of the classics, student-centered methodologies are the ones that most stimulate their interest and motivation, while boosting their literary competency (Shoemaker, 2013; Wood, 2017). To do so, teachers mainly rely on dialogic activities, in which students can share their own perspective instead of repeating the teacher's. This literary transaction (Rosenblatt, 1938) is also ideal for developing 'critical literacy', which lets students address compelling social issues (Dyches, 2018, Steiss, 2020).

The teacher's role is crucial in establishing a parallel between the horizon of expectations (Jauss, 1982) of a classic work and that of the students. Thus, even when following a methodology centred on student involvement, the teacher must serve as a guide, especially when students lack the knowledge and skills necessary for higher-level tasks. Therefore, the importance of the mediator to how students learn validates the relevance of a study focused on teacher beliefs.

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